

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

THE INFLUENCE OF OSMOTIC PRESSURE ON THE STABILITY OF BOREHOLE WALLS

Abbasov S.

Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University,
Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

Osmotic pressure (denoted by π) is the excess hydrostatic pressure of a solution separated from a pure solvent by a semipermeable membrane, at which diffusion of the solvent through the membrane (osmosis) ceases. This pressure tends to equalize the concentrations of both solutions due to the counter diffusion of solute and solvent molecules.

Osmotic phenomena in a well may occur under certain conditions. For this it is necessary to form a barrier permeable to the solvent and impermeable to the dissolved substance. When osmotic phenomena occur, high pressure arises in the wall clay layer, caused by very low permeability of the rocks. Stress occurs immediately behind the crust and in the adjacent rock layer, causing the destruction of this layer and the crust. This creates significant caverns, causing the collapse of the overlying rocks, which can lead to serious complications during well construction.

Keywords: Osmotic phenomena, uncased part of the well, excess pressure, clay crusts, osmotic pressure, specific gravity, stress state.

Problem setup and solution of the problem

Let's assume the open-hole section of a well penetrates a rock layer pores of which are filled with water. It is known that the outgoing flow of drilling fluid, while transporting cuttings from the bottomhole to the wellhead, simultaneously performs another important function: it causes clay formation on the walls of the uncased borehole. This is achieved due to the ability of the drilling fluid, under the influence of excess pressure, to filter the liquid phase into the pores or fractures of the rock.

If the sizes of the pores and suspension particles are comparable, then, upon contact with the porous medium, a crust of filtered clay particles is formed at its boundary, which densifies relatively quickly and prevents penetration of drilling fluid into the formation pores.

It has been determined that when solutions move through fractures, a phase separation occurs, i.e., bound water converted to a free state. Moreover, the smaller the crack opening, the greater the intensity of the transition. This phenomenon is particularly evident in chemically untreated solutions [1, 2].

By separating formation fluids, clay crusts act as membranes that allow only solvent to pass through. Water freed from impurities in the pores becomes a solvent and returns through the clay cake to the wellbore. This process continues until the concentrations on both sides of the crust are equal. Considering that the concentration of drilling fluid in the wellbore is restored by upwardly moving cuttings particles, the process of pure

water—the solvent—penetrating into the wellbore continues indefinitely. As a result of this process, the pressure inside the wellbore increases, while behind the clay crust the pressure drops. The pressure difference created in this way is called osmotic pressure. Osmotic pressure is usually denoted by π and defined by the Vanthoff formula [3].

$$\pi = CRT \quad (1)$$

where R is the gas constant; T - the average temperature of the drilling fluid, C - concentration of the solution, mol/l .

Osmotic pressure can reach significant values; for example, for seawater, it is approximately $2.8 MPa$. Therefore, osmotic pressure is currently considered a possible cause of rock instability in the wellbore zone and associated complications. Let's determine the stresses in clay crusts caused by osmotic pressure. A clay crust is a cylindrical body with pressure acting on its inner surface.

$$P_1 = \gamma_m h + P + \pi \quad (2)$$

where h is the drilling depth of the well, γ_m - the specific gravity of the drilling mud, P - the excess pressure created to force the drilling mud particles upward.

There is soil pressure acting from the outside $P_2 = P_g$

The determination of stresses arising in the clay crust is reduced to the solution of the Lamé problem.

Therefore, for plane deformation, the stress state in a cylindrical coordinate system is determined as follows [5]:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_r = -\frac{1}{b^2 - a^2} \left[P_2 b^2 \left(1 - \frac{a^2}{r^2} \right) + P_1 a^2 \left(\frac{b^2}{r^2} - 1 \right) \right] \\ \sigma_\varphi = -\frac{1}{b^2 - a^2} \left[P_2 b^2 \left(1 + \frac{a^2}{r^2} \right) - P_1 a^2 \left(\frac{b^2}{r^2} + 1 \right) \right] \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_z = \nu(\sigma_r + \sigma_\varphi)$$

$$At r = A,$$

$$\sigma_r = -P_1, \sigma_\varphi = -\frac{1}{1-k^2} [2P_2 - P_1(1+k^2)], \sigma_z = -\frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu(P_2 + k^2P_1)$$

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_r = -P_1, \\ \sigma_\varphi = -\frac{1}{1-k^2} [2P_2 - P_1(1+k^2)] \\ \sigma_z = -\frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu(P_2 + k^2P_1) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where $\sigma_r, \sigma_\varphi, \sigma_z$ are stress components; a and b – the inner and outer radii of the clay crust, respectively; r – the current radial coordinate.

The failure condition is known to have the form [6]

$$J_1^2 + 2(1+\nu)J_2 = 2\sigma_y^2 \quad (5)$$

where J_1, J_2 are the first and second invariants of the stress tensor, respectively; ν – Poisson's ratio; σ_y – yield strength of the clay crust.

Then we calculate J_1 and J_2 at $r = a$ because, regardless of the boundary conditions, destruction begins from the inside;

$$J_1 = \sigma_r + \sigma_\varphi + \sigma_z = (1+\nu)(\sigma_r + \sigma_\varphi) = -\frac{2(1+\nu)}{1-k^2} P_2$$

$$J_2 = -(\sigma_y\sigma_\varphi + \sigma_r\sigma_z + \sigma_z\sigma_\varphi) =$$

$$= -\frac{1}{1-k^2} [2P_1P_2 - P_1^2 - k^2P_1^2 + 2\nu P_1P_2 + 2\nu k^2P_1^2 +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 4\nu P_2^2 - \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu P_1P_2 - \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu k^2P_1P_2 +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 4\nu k^2P_1P_2 - \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu k^2P_1^2 - \frac{1}{1-k^2} \cdot 2\nu k^4P_1^2]$$

If to denote $\frac{1}{1-k^2} = m$, then we get

$$J_1 = -\frac{2(1+\nu)}{1-k^2} P_2 = -2m^2(1+\nu)P_2 \quad (6)$$

$$J_2 = -m^2 [2P_1P_2 - P_1^2 - k^2P_1^2 + 2\nu P_1P_2 + 2\nu k^2P_1^2 + m^2 \cdot 4\nu P_2^2 -$$

$$- m^2 \cdot 2\nu P_1P_2 - m^2 \cdot 2\nu k^2P_1P_2 + m^2 \cdot 4\nu k^2P_1P_2 - m^2 \cdot 2\nu k^2P_1^2 - m^2 \cdot 2\nu k^4P_1^2] \quad (7)$$

The destruction condition is known to have the form [6]:

$$J_1^2 + 2(1+\nu)J_2 = 2\sigma_y^2 \quad (8)$$

If to take values of J_1 and J_2 into account in (8), we obtain an equation of the second order with respect to P_1 .

$$P_1^2 [2m^2(1+\nu) + 2m^2k^2(1+\nu) - 4m^2\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 4m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 4m^4\nu k^4(1+\nu)] -$$

$$- [P_1P_2(4m^2(1+\nu) + 4m^2\nu(1+\nu) - 4m^4\nu(1+\nu) - 4m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 8m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu)) +$$

$$+ P_2^2 [4m^4(1+\nu)^2 - 8m^4k^2(1+\nu)]] = 2\sigma_y^2$$

If to introduce the following notations;

$$2m^2(1+\nu) + 2m^2k^2(1+\nu) - 4m^2\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 4m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 4m^4\nu k^4(1+\nu) = A$$

$$P_1P_2(4m^2(1+\nu) + 4m^2\nu(1+\nu) - 4m^4\nu(1+\nu) - 4m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu) + 8m^4\nu k^2(1+\nu)) = B$$

$$4m^4(1+\nu)^2 - 8m^4k^2(1+\nu) = C$$

Then the equation will take the form;

$$AP_1^2 - BP_1P_2 + CP_2^2 - 2\sigma_y^2 = 0$$

General solutions to this equation

$$P_1 = \frac{BP_2 \pm \sqrt{B^2P_2^2 - 4A(CP_2^2 - 2\sigma_y^2)}}{2A} \quad (9)$$

In order for equation (9) to have a real solution, the following conditions must be satisfied; $B^2P_2^2 - 4A(CP_2^2 - 2\sigma_y^2) \geq 0$ (10)

By solving (10) we obtain the permissible value of drilling depth for a given soil.

$$P_2 \leq \frac{8A\sigma_y^2}{4AC - B^2}$$

Knowing that, $P_2 = \gamma h_a$

$$\gamma h_a \leq \frac{8A\sigma_y^2}{4AC - B^2}$$

Taking into account (2) we can determine the critical value of excess pressure of a given soil.

$$P_k = \frac{BP_2 - \sqrt{B^2P_2^2 - 4A(CP_2^2 - 2\sigma_y^2)}}{2A} - \gamma_m - \pi$$

The influence of osmotic pressure on the stability of the walls of the uncased part of the well, taking into account the formation pressure.

Let us suppose that in the downhole section there is a formation pressure, which is determined as follows:

$$P_0 = \gamma_W h \quad (10)$$

where γ_W is the specific gravity of groundwater, h – drilling depth.

In practice, during the drilling process, for safety reasons, when preparing the drilling mud, equality $\gamma_r \approx \gamma_m$ is ensured between the reduced specific gravity of the rock γ_r and the specific gravity of the drilling mud γ_m . Therefore, a stress state arises in the crust due to the borehole pressure and its own weight. Then, the boundary conditions will take the form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \text{at } r = a \quad \sigma_r &= -(P + CRT) = -P_1 \\ \text{at } r = b \quad \sigma_r &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (11)$$

Similar to the problem discussed above, the stress state in the crust is determined as follows;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= -\frac{a^2 b^2 P_1}{b^2 - a^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{a^2 P_1}{b^2 - a^2} - \gamma_r h \\ \sigma_\varphi &= -\frac{a^2 b^2 P_1}{b^2 - a^2} \cdot \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{a^2 P_1}{b^2 - a^2} - \gamma_r h \\ \sigma_z &= -2\nu \frac{a^2 P_1}{b^2 - a^2} - \gamma_r h \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (12)$$

where γ_r is the reduced specific gravity of the rock, which is determined as follows;

$$\gamma_r = \gamma_a + (\gamma_B - \gamma_r) e_0$$

where γ_r – the specific gravity of the rock lying at depth h ; P – the excess pressure created for the circulation of the drilling mud, e_0 – the porosity of the soil.

Early plastic deformations occur on the inner surface of the crust. Stresses $r = a$ will take the form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_r &= -P_1 - \gamma_n h \\ \sigma_\varphi &= \frac{(1 - k^2)}{1 - k^2} P_1 - \gamma_n h \\ \sigma_z &= 2\nu \frac{k^2}{1 - k^2} P_1 - \gamma_n h \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (13)$$

If to take into account (12) in the destruction condition (5), we obtain a second-order algebraic equation with respect to P_1 :

$$\frac{3}{(1 - k^2)^3} P_1^2 = 2\sigma_{y.S}^2 \quad (14)$$

where σ_{nT} is the reduced yield strength, which is determined as follows;

$$\sigma_{y.S} = \sigma_y (1 - e_0)$$

The solution to equation (14) is as follows:

$$P_1 = \left| \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}} (1 - k^2) \sigma_{y.S} \right| \quad (15)$$

(5) determines the critical value of the wellbore pressure at which the crust is destroyed.

We will solve this problem for some rocks. The crust thickness is $d = 7$ mm, the crust radius of curvature $r_0 = 100$ is mm, $k = 0,935$,

Sandstones. $e_0 = 0,05 \div 0,25$

Fig. 1 Graph of the dependence $e_0 - h$
1. $\sigma_y = 30$ Mpa, 2. $\sigma_y = 50$ MPa, 3. $\sigma_y = 70$ MPa.

Limestone. $e_0 = 0,02 \div 0,3$

Fig. 2 Graph of the dependence $e_0 - h$
1. $\sigma_y = 100 \text{ MPa}$, 2. $\sigma_y = 150 \text{ MPa}$, 3. $\sigma_y = 170 \text{ MPa}$.

Anhydride $e_0 = 0,4 \div 0,5$

Fig. 3 Graph of the dependence $e_0 - h$
 $\sigma_y = 150 \text{ MPa}$, 2. $\sigma_y = 170 \text{ MPa}$, 3. $\sigma_y = 170 \text{ MPa}$.

CONCLUSIONS

The work presents a mathematical modeling of the mechanical characteristics of a porous body when osmotic pressure acts within its pores.

An analytical expression has been obtained for determining the excess pressure at which safe well drilling is possible.

References

1. Emtsev V. T. Microbiology: a textbook for universities / V. T. Emtsev, E. N. Mishustin - 5th edition, revised and supplemented - Moscow: Drofa, 2005., p. 445.
2. Lysak V.V., Microbiology: a textbook / V.V. Lysak. - Minsk: BSU, 2007, p. 430.
3. Pilkevich N.B., Vinogradov A.A., Boyarchuk E.D. Fundamentals of Microbiology: A Textbook for

Students of Higher Education Institutions. – Lugansk: Alma Mater, 2008. p. 192.

4. I. Esmen, G. G. Gabuzov. Thermohydraulic processes during well drilling. Moscow: Nauka, 1991, p. 216.

5. Yu. A. Amenzade. Theory of elasticity. Moscow: "Higher School", 1976, p. 272.

6. Orucov Y.A., Abbasov S.H., "Analytical determination of the critical value of well flow rate during flowing operation": Theory and Applications, Special Issue No. 6 (80), Part-1, Volume 19, December 2024 <https://gnedenko.net/Journal/>.

7. Iskandarov, E.Kh., Ismayilova, F.B., Shukurly, M.F., Ismayilova, P.Sh. Changes in energy characteristics of pipeline systems considering hydrodynamic loads *SOCAR Proceedings*, 2024, (2), pp. 105–108 DOI: 10.5510/OGP20240200974